

The Multi-omics Toolbox (MOTBX): Empowering Multi-omics Research and Analysis for the Translational Medicine Community

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Abstract

Personalised medicine (PM) research seeks to identify interventions that can be targeted to individual patients based on their predicted response. Efficient advancement of PM depends on the availability of validated patient-targeted biomarkers. To deliver them, we need a more precise understanding of the molecular profiles of individuals, which is facilitated by multi-omics approaches. To turn the multi-omics promises into a reality, systemic bottlenecks impacting the biomarker field need to be overcome. As part of the EATRIS-Plus project, we developed the Multi-omics Toolbox (MOTBX), to support the translational medicine research community by providing validated resources, such as standardised protocols for individual omics performance and analysis, quality, and data management guidelines, for the development, the implementation and the adoption of multi-omics approaches in real PM. The MOTBX is a resource that has been built *with*, and *for* the community. This means that researchers are not only welcome to use the MOTBX, but to support its further development by actively contributing with valuable resources.

Challenges in the realm of multi-omics research

Genetic studies have provided a useful framework for mapping and studying specific genetic variants contributing to both Mendelian and complex diseases [1]. On the contrary, for advancing personalised medicine (PM) a more precise understanding of the molecular profiles is needed [2]. In fact, PM has been successfully applied in the areas where strong genetic drivers provide a platform for developing genomic biomarkers and associated therapies, for example in oncology [3–5] and rare diseases [6–8]. However, to apply PM to other disease domains a multi-omics approach is needed as the biology of these disorders is multi-factorial and complex from a biological point of view.

The omics field has largely been driven by technological advances that have made cost-efficient, high-throughput analysis of biological molecules possible. Compared to single -omics interrogations, multi-omics can provide researchers with a greater understanding of the flow of information, from disease aetiology (genetic, environmental, and/or developmental) to the functional phenotypes and consequences or relevant interactions [9–11].

Multi-omics approaches also have far-reaching implications for drug discovery and drug repurposing providing the opportunity to identify and validate drug targets and common mechanisms. They allow the development of biomarkers for treatment selection to maximise therapy effects with minimal toxicity, and to create and explore multi-modal therapies tailored to the needs of the individual patient [12,13].

However, there are still a number of challenges confronting the multi-omics research community that need to be addressed in order to advance the field of biomarker development[14,15]:

- Harmonisation of technological and analytical gold standard methods and protocols
- Low-quality data stewardship and awareness of the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles, in the context of multi-omics research
- Lack of high-quality gold standards for multi-omics datasets
- Lack of reliable control reference values for multi-omics biomarkers in healthy populations
- Validated and standardised pipelines for multi-omics data integrated analysis (data coming from different biological layers).

The EATRIS Multi-omics Toolbox (MOTBX): a knowledge hub for finding and accessing resources for the development, the implementation, and the adoption of multi-omics approaches in PM

Tackling these issues systematically was a crucial objective of the H2020 project, [EATRIS-Plus](#) [14] under which umbrella the EATRIS Multi-omics Toolbox (MOTBX) was designed and built.

The EATRIS MOTBX (Figure 1) is an open access web resource to help support translational research by making it easier for researchers in academia and industry to find relevant resources related to multi-omics analysis. The EATRIS MOTBX aims to serve as a single-entry point for translational researchers, clinicians, and science providers to obtain centralised access and information on multi-omics technologies protocols, data analysis, management tools and quality guidelines.

Figure 1: The EATRIS Multi-omics Toolbox (MOTBX), a knowledge hub for clinicians and translational researchers from academia and industry

The -omics tools have been developed and applied in two real-world scenarios. Firstly, resources provided within the EATRIS MOTBX were applied in an established cohort of one hundred healthy individuals in Czechia with genome sequences available. Information available on this healthy individual cohort has been augmented during the project with transcriptomic, proteomic and metabolomic data.

Secondly, the EATRIS MOTBX resources were applied for data quality control and statistical analyses, in a cross-omics study, a study that integrates different omics data, to analyse a cohort of 150 trios of paediatric patients suffering from neurodevelopmental disorders, together with their parents, for genetic variants using whole genome and exome sequencing. After stringent quality assessment of the plasma samples, forty suitable patients-parent trios were selected and was investigated for metabolic changes of a comprehensive targeted metabolite biomarker panel using mass spectrometry.

By providing such a toolbox to the research community, EATRIS is the engine to enable high-quality multi-omics research and accelerate the implementation of PM solutions. Indeed, EATRIS MOTBX is a nuclear resource for several projects of Personalized Medicine currently ongoing.

The EATRIS MOTBX provides resources related to multiple -omics technologies (genomics, epigenomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics), including quality control and assessment, and data stewardship and integration. The toolbox offers:

- A collection of best practices and protocols for individual –omics technologies
- Resources to help implement quality control and quality assessment processes.
- Tools and services to adopt FAIR data practices for multi-omics data management and analysis.
- Education and training resources in multi-omics field
- Links to other EATRIS Toolkits, e.g., [Patient Engagement Resource Centre \(PERC\)](#), [Innovation Management Toolbox \(EJPRD IMT\)](#)

Improving usability of EATRIS MOTBX

The development of the EATRIS MOTBX started with the creation of a dedicated scientific and management team of experts that since September 2022 met regularly with the aim to bring the vision of the EATRIS MOTBX into the reality. The EATRIS MOTBX team is made of scientists with various type and level of expertise, such as multi-omics research, data science, clinical research, website developer, some of them already part of the EATRIS-Plus consortium. The EATRIS MOTBX team put together bricks and brain to develop a useful and sustainable resources to answer the specific needs of the multi-omics community.

Once the prototype was ready, to produce a high-quality and user-friendly service, a User Experience (UX) testing session for the EATRIS MOTBX was conducted in a structured online manner, involving five participants with two moderators from EATRIS MOTBX team. The participants represented a diverse range of expertise and backgrounds: two computational biologists with experience in single-cell –omics and multi-omics analyses; a medical doctor, also PhD, specialising in clinical management and clinical trials using omics a PhD student working with transcriptomics data; and a genomics research senior scientist and diagnostic providers. The session focused on assessing the user experience and functionalities of the EATRIS MOTBX. The workshop aimed to gather valuable user insights and feedback to enhance the usability and functionality of the Multi-omics Toolbox.

The workshop's objective was to comprehend user interactions and impressions of the website over a 45-50-minute duration. Participants were not given access to the toolbox beforehand. An essential outcome of the UX testing was to assess the user experience without prior knowledge to assess the current state, identify pain points, and improve the toolbox based on direct user feedback.

The testing process was segmented into three distinct tasks, each designed to elicit varied perspectives on the service. The first task focused on understanding the toolbox's purpose and evaluating basic

navigation capabilities. Participants were asked to share initial impressions, explore the EATRIS MOTBX offerings, and demonstrate navigational actions such as searching for specific resources. The second task revolved around quality control, wherein participants explored how the toolbox could assist a hypothetical research organisation in enhancing the quality and reliability of preclinical research and in seeking information on certification related to external quality assessment such as the one offered by the Luxembourg Institute of Health proficiency testing programme. The final task delved into multi-omics data management and analysis, requiring participants to locate guidance on data management and the FAIR data principles.

Throughout the workshop, participants were encouraged to verbalise their actions and thoughts while sharing their screens, and consent was sought for recording the session for further internal review. Observations were made regarding the use of tags, categories, and filters during navigation of the toolbox. The data collected from this session was crucial in identifying and implementing potential enhancements to the toolbox website. Participants were highly motivated providing even further feedback and material days after the workshop,

Following the participant-driven workshop, the toolbox underwent an additional evaluation stage in the form of an external UX expert review. This stage was integral to ensuring a holistic and professional assessment of the platform. The UX expert thoroughly evaluated the toolbox from a user-centric perspective, evaluating the interface, navigation flow, content organisation, and overall user experience. Their analysis complemented the insights gathered from the initial workshop, contributing to a more technical and specialised perspective. By combining the real-time feedback from participants with the expert review, the development team aimed to identify a comprehensive set of potential enhancements to ensure the toolbox is not only user-friendly but also adheres to the standards of UX design.

Both the insights from the participant workshop and the independent evaluation by UX experts proved invaluable in guiding the development of the toolbox. For instance, the outcomes of the UX testing and review directly influenced improvements in the layout and category naming of resources, resulting in refinement of sub-category classifications, enhanced search functionality, and a streamlined, efficient reporting process for resources with broken links. These updates have significantly enhanced the usability and overall effectiveness of the toolbox.

The EATRIS MOTBX technical workflow

To ensure that the EATRIS MOTBX content continues to reflect the state of the art and to provide comprehensive coverage about multi-omics analysis in translational research, whilst simultaneously minimising the need for overheads of technical maintenance and data errors, we describe here the technical implementation of the content workflow.

The technical implementation follows the following criteria:

- Facilitate community engagement and EATRIS MOTBX content suggestions from the EATRIS community in a bottom-up approach.
- (Semi-)automated addition of content from external databases
- Automation of processes: tracking changes, validating content, updating the website
- Updating the content based on the validated resources uploaded by EATRIS MOTBX users

From the technical perspective, the implementation uses version control, input formats are both human- and machine-readable, and the content workflow is semi-automated. To implement the workflow, we created a GitHub repository: <https://github.com/EATRIS/motbx>. GitHub is a cloud-based platform that uses Git, a version control software that allows tracking changes to files in the repository. All [EATRIS MOTBX resources produced and collected from the EATRIS-Plus project](#), and those suggested by the EATRIS working groups are stored in this repository in YAML format. This format allows validation of the data/content structure against a specified schema which is stored in the JSON schema format. This ensures that the format of the submitted resources is compliant with the requirements of the MOTBX website, e.g., resources need to have a title, category, and description, and valid and live links (URLs). The GitHub repository also contains the source code that performs such validation tasks using the automated GitHub actions.

Automated actions are:

- Validation of resources that are added or changed
- Scheduled summaries of the current resources
- Possibility of scheduled searches of external databases to automatically add content based on pre-defined search queries

Editing or adding resources via platform, project, or community

Any edits or additions can be suggested via the EATRIS MOTBX website or directly on GitHub by creating an Issue (<https://github.com/EATRIS/motbx/issues/new/choose>). Suggestions will be reviewed by the EATRIS MOTBX Team and approved or rejected based on scientific, quality, and strategic criteria. Any new content should be extensively validated by the scientific community and represent and add value for the resource. Approved suggestions result in the revision or creation of a resource YAML file.

Editing or adding resources via external databases

The EATRIS MOTBX can semi-automatically pull resources from existing resources via pre-defined queries that search external databases (e.g., FAIRsharing.org, bio.tools) programmatically using Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). The queries depend on the underlying data model of the

database to be searched. Query results are converted automatically to the EATRIS MOTBX data format. The searches are performed at scheduled intervals and results are reviewed and approved by the EATRIS MOTBX Team, following pre-established criteria prior to being published as authenticated resources available via EATRIS MOTBX.

The EATRIS MOTBX resource schema

The following elements are mandatory for all resources available from the EATRIS MOTBX:

- Unique resource ID (added by the EATRIS MOTBX Team via the Git repository)
- Title
- Category
- Subcategory
- Description
- URL
- Tags
- Keywords (for search functionality)

Generation of the EATRIS MOTBX in collaboration with the Translational Medicine community

The first workshop, a pivotal event aimed at engaging EATRIS MOTBX stakeholders, notably industry experts, occurred on September 27th, 2023. During the workshop, the EATRIS MOTBX was introduced elucidating its utility and unveiling additional requirements and aspirations as articulated by key opinion leaders from the prominent multi-omics initiative.

The workshop objectives were to:

- Present the resource to a broad range of community representatives from Europe and USA
- Inform about the EATRIS MOTBX and present its main functionalities
- Understand expectations around the EATRIS MOTBX
- Retrieve the needs and dreams from the key opinion leader and use these to further the development and sustainability of EATRIS MOTBX
- Connect with other initiatives for exploring synergies

During the meeting, the participants were invited to answer the following five questions:

1. *What research challenges would you expect the EATRIS MOTBX to help you and your colleagues overcome?*
2. *Would you use or recommend the EATRIS MOTBX to your colleagues?*

3. *Are you aware of other tools and/or ongoing initiatives similar to the EATRIS MOTBX? How can the EATRIS MOTBX connect with these initiatives?*
4. *How can you support the future development of the EATRIS MOTBX?*
5. *Do you have general comments, ideas, or aspirations for improving the EATRIS MOTBX?*

Among the challenges discussed, the most prominent issues include the absence of established best practices for crafting standard protocols, the lack of references to guidelines and regulations, and the dearth of standardized procedures for validating AI models in the context of omics data. Additionally, a noteworthy challenge is the need for harmonization of metadata to facilitate the seamless integration of multi-omics datasets. To encourage broader adoption of multi-omics tools among researchers and clinicians, thereby pushing the boundaries of PM beyond genomics and extending its advantages to a larger patient population, addressing the specific challenges outlined by the workshop participants is paramount. Tackling these detailed challenges will significantly propel the field forward.

Workshop participants emphasized the potential of the EATRIS MOTBX tool but underscored the necessity for validation and enhancement. This involves incorporating a more diverse range of information from various scientific disciplines, including medical images such as radiological and pathological data.

In general, the feedback was positive, and the reception of EATRIS MOTBX was favourable. Stakeholders actively engaged in the workshop expressed their commitment to supporting the tool's dissemination and subsequent development. Additionally, they put forth proposals for collaborative synergies with existing initiatives that were identified during the session.

Long-term sustainability of the EATRIS MOTBX

In order to ensure the long-term stability and sustainability of the EATRIS MOTBX, i.e. beyond the duration of the EATRIS-Plus project, EATRIS-ERIC will promote the dissemination and use of the service as well as contribute to its content development, through various activities of its [Biomarkers Platform](#).

The EATRIS Biomarkers Platform is a network of 86+ institutions across Europe that facilitates the validation and development of biomarkers for the prevention, diagnosis, and prognostic assessment of disease as well as for the prediction of therapy response.

The EATRIS Biomarkers Platform's strategy for the coming years is to focus on multimodal biomarkers development and validation and artificial intelligence (AI) approaches that combine and integrate multiple sources of biomarker data (from digital and wet laboratory research) for enabling the

translation of patient-specific characteristics into tailored clinical applications (i.e., PM) as well as for assisting clinical decision-making.

The final aim of the Biomarkers Platform is the development of biomarker-guided targeted medicines. AI approaches will lead to the optimization of the effectiveness of biomarker signatures for targeted interventions, by considering the specific individual biology (e.g., genetic, biochemical, phenotypic, lifestyle, and psychosocial characteristics). This approach is the natural development of -omics disciplines that use high-throughput screening tools aimed at detailed collecting, characterising, and integrating comprehensive pools of biological molecules (DNA sequences, transcripts, miRNAs, proteins/peptides, metabolites/lipids) that relate to individual humans. The EATRIS MOTBX content and materials will be crucial for the biomarkers platform achievements and strategy, although the other 4 EATRIS platforms could benefit too.

Next to the Biomarkers Platform, the long-term sustainability of the EATRIS MOTBX and the evolution of its content available to the user community will be ensured by including the EATRIS MOTBX in ongoing and new EATRIS projects and activities, as well as in the EATRIS member institutions. Additionally, EATRIS national nodes activity could be also an opportunity for dissemination and maintenance of the EATRIS MOTBX. Moreover, the EATRIS MOTBX and other EATRIS toolkits will be fundamental for pillar 4 development: awareness about EATRIS.

Ongoing projects, such as [REMEDI4ALL](#), are poised to leverage the EATRIS MOTBX and support its application in specific use cases. The outcomes will directly contribute to the content of the EATRIS MOTBX and provide success stories that can be utilised as part of outreach activities to attract new users to the service. This concept is transferrable to the EATRIS' Digital Transformation strategic direction and activities.

Project-related publications will cite the EATRIS MOTBX, and an accurate dissemination and publication strategy will ensure the engagement of new stakeholders and users through a variety of communication channels.

The EATRIS MOTBX will be included in new project proposals, where applicable. New consortia will utilize and expand the resources and services of the EATRIS MOTBX, ensuring its continued development in specific areas. For instance, in cases involving consortia building efforts focused on developing novel technologies in a specific -omics field, we can offer the EATRIS MOTBX as a central resource to facilitate high-quality research, and in turn, incorporate the future outputs of these new projects into the EATRIS MOTBX.

Additionally, EATRIS members will play a key role in promoting the EATRIS MOTBX at local and regional events, and engage with experts and key opinion leaders in various omics approaches to support the content development and adoption of the EATRIS MOTBX tool.

The EATRIS MOTBX: a resource built by, *with*, and *for* the community.

The EATRIS MOTBX is a valuable resource developed to address specific needs and challenges in the field of multi-omics research within the translational medicine (TM) community. However, this journey is just beginning. It is crucial for clinicians and translational researchers to come together and share their knowledge and expertise on multi-omics approaches and applications to support the maturation of this field. Therefore, we invite the community to use and contribute to the EATRIS MOTBX. Together with the support of the users and the wider TM community, we remain confident to enhance and sustain the EATRIS MOTBX, making it a valuable resource collaboratively built *with*, and *for* the community.

The EATRIS MOTBX offers substantial added value to the research community, particularly in the realms of good practices, harmonisation, and standardisation. These aspects play a crucial role in overcoming the principal bottlenecks hindering the effective translation of scientific discoveries to clinical practice.

The EATRIS MOTBX service addresses this challenge by promoting and implementing good practices that ensure the reliability and reproducibility of research outcomes. By establishing a framework for harmonisation and standardisation, EATRIS MOTBX facilitates the development of consistent methodologies and protocols across different laboratories and research settings.

This commitment to standardised practices not only enhances the robustness of research findings, but also streamlines the process of knowledge transfer from the laboratory to the clinical setting. Clinicians and researchers benefit from having access to resources in one single point of entry and can actively participate in the development of the EATRIS MOTBX. This collaborative approach is pivotal in breaking down silos and ensuring a more cohesive and effective progression of research from the bench to the bedside.

References

- 1 Shendure J, Findlay GM, Snyder MW. Genomic medicine -- progress, pitfalls, and promise. *Cell* 2019;**177**:45. doi:10.1016/J.CELL.2019.02.003
- 2 Olivier M, Asmis R, Hawkins GA, *et al.* The need for multi-omics biomarker signatures in precision medicine. *Int J Mol Sci* 2019;**20**. doi:10.3390/ijms20194781
- 3 Syn NLX, Yong WP, Goh BC, *et al.* Evolving landscape of tumor molecular profiling for personalized cancer therapy: a comprehensive review. *Expert Opin Drug Metab Toxicol* 2016;**12**:911–22. doi:10.1080/17425255.2016.1196187
- 4 Chen HZ, Bonneville R, Roychowdhury S. Implementing precision cancer medicine in the genomic era. *Semin Cancer Biol* 2019;**55**:16–27. doi:10.1016/j.semcancer.2018.05.009
- 5 Berger MF, Mardis ER. The emerging clinical relevance of genomics in cancer medicine. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol* 2018;**15**:353–65. doi:10.1038/S41571-018-0002-6
- 6 Baynam G, Bowman F, Lister K, *et al.* Improved diagnosis and care for rare diseases through implementation of precision public health framework. *Adv Exp Med Biol* 2017;**1031**:55–94. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-67144-4_4
- 7 Alves ITS, Condinho M, Custódio S, *et al.* Genetics of personalized medicine: cancer and rare diseases. *Cell Oncol (Dordr)* 2018;**41**:335–41. doi:10.1007/S13402-018-0379-3
- 8 Klein C, Gahl WA. Patients with rare diseases: from therapeutic orphans to pioneers of personalized treatments. *EMBO Mol Med* 2018;**10**:1–3. doi:10.15252/emmm.201708365
- 9 Chung RH, Kang CY. A multi-omics data simulator for complex disease studies and its application to evaluate multi-omics data analysis methods for disease classification. *Gigascience* 2019;**8**. doi:10.1093/gigascience/giz045
- 10 Pineda S, Gomez-Rubio P, Picornell A, *et al.* Framework for the Integration of Genomics, Epigenomics and Transcriptomics in Complex Diseases. *Hum Hered* 2015;**79**:124–36. doi:10.1159/000381184
- 11 Sun Y V., Hu YJ. Integrative Analysis of Multi-omics Data for Discovery and Functional Studies of Complex Human Diseases. *Adv Genet* 2016;**93**:147–90. doi:10.1016/BS.ADGEN.2015.11.004
- 12 Dar MA, Arafah A, Bhat KA, *et al.* Multiomics technologies: Role in disease biomarker discoveries and therapeutics. *Brief Funct Genomics* 2023;**22**:76–96. doi:10.1093/bfgp/elac017
- 13 Nassar SF, Raddassi K, Wu T. Single-Cell Multiomics Analysis for Drug Discovery.

Metabolites 2021;**11**. doi:10.3390/METABO11110729

- 14 Oldoni E, Saunders G, Bietrix F, *et al.* Tackling the translational challenges of multi-omics research in the realm of European personalised medicine: A workshop report. *Front Mol Biosci* 2022;**9**. doi:10.3389/FMOLB.2022.974799
- 15 Tarazona S, Arzalluz-Luque A, Conesa A. Undisclosed, unmet and neglected challenges in multi-omics studies. *Nat Comput Sci* 2021 16 2021;**1**:395–402. doi:10.1038/s43588-021-00086-z